

The Effectiveness Of Structured Teaching Program On Identification And Management Of Nomo Phobia Among Basic B.Sc. Nursing Students At Selected College Of Nursing In Bengaluru

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Abstract-

Background: The digital revolution has changed the way we live. Life without cell phones for many are unthinkable.¹Nomo phobia is a term describing a growing fear in today's world- the fear of being without a mobile device or beyond the cell phone contact. Among today's high school and college students it's on the rise.

Methods: A pre-experimental one group pre-test post-test study design adopted by convenient sampling technique, 60 B.Sc. nursing students were selected for the study. The tool comprised of two sections: Section A: Socio demographic data containing 12 items. Section B: 34 items on identification and management on nomophobia

Result: In overall knowledge, the mean% pre- test knowledge was 54.167% with SD 14.217%. The mean% post-test knowledge found to be 82.843% with SD 7.888%. The enhancement was proved as mean (28.676%) and SD of (8.768%). Further, the paired t-test value (25.312) shows statistical significance at level of $p < 0.001$ with df (59), establishing the effectiveness of treatment.

Conclusion: The present study showed that B.Sc. nursing students have no absolute knowledge on identification and management of nomophobia. Structured teaching program was found to be effective to enhance their knowledge. The study concluded that, necessary awareness programme will enhance the knowledge of health personnel.

Keywords: Assess, Knowledge, Structured Teaching Program, Nomophobia and B.Sc. Nursing Students.

INTRODUCTION

Nomo Phobia is thought to be a trend in only developed and technologically advanced countries. However, it is also identified in India by psychiatrists' particularly in adolescence and adults who are addicted to smart phones. It refers to discomfort, anxiety, nervousness, ringxiety, anguish caused being out of contact with a mobile phone.² Across the world it's an anxiety which people face when they feel they could not get a signal from mobile tower, run out battery and forget to take the phones with them or simply do not receive call or text or email notification for a certain period of time. In short it's a psychological fear of losing mobile or cell contact.³

Studies conducted in various regions of India have shown addictive behaviours related to smart phone use among young adults. Even so the severity and related behaviour is under rated and unnoticed in India, because the smart phone use is widely considered an ordinary and necessary behaviour. Smart phone can be used for variety of purposes, calls, texts, paying bills, making online transactions etc. in such a scenario identifying deviant behaviour becomes an almost impossible task.

The number of smart phone users in India is doubled to 859 million by 2022 from 468 million users in 2017 growing at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 12.9% according to an ASSOCHAM-PwC joint study.⁴ Karnataka has around 709 mobile users per thousand populations whereas internet users are 8-9% of total population. Similarly, at the all India level there are 600 million unique subscribers with around 900 million total subscriptions.⁵

IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

Nomo Phobia the fear or anxiety of being away from mobile phone contact is considered a disorder of the contemporary digital and virtual society that refers to discomfort and anxiety and nervousness or anguish caused by being out contact with a mobile phone or a computer.⁶ Nomo phobia is everywhere in industrialized nations. A study conducted by market analysis and consumer research organization(MACRO) in Mumbai to study the various patterns and association of mobile phone usage reported that 58% of the respondents could not manage without a mobile phone even for a day.⁷

New time mobility poll reported that 84% people could not go a single day without their mobile devices. Around 206 published survey reports suggest that 50% of teens and 27% of parents feel that they are addicted to mobiles. The recent studies also reported the increase of mobile phone dependence and this could increase internet addiction. Overuse of mobile phones may cause physiological illness such as dry eyes, computer vision syndrome, weakness of thumb and wrist, neck pain and rigidity, increased frequency of De Quervain's tenosynovitis, tactile hallucination, Nomo phobia, insecurity, delusions, auditory sleep disturbances, insomnia, hallucinations, lower self-confidence and mobile phone addiction disorders.⁸ Most of the Nomo phobic experience ringxiety also known as phantom vibration syndrome or phantom ringing which means a fall sensation of ringing of the mobile phones.⁹ Considering the tremendous growth in the smart phone market it is but threatening to imagine the dependency that Indians would face with their mobile device. Thus this emerging trend of excessive smart phone usage challenges the wellbeing of population. At this point, knowledge of prevalence of Nomo Phobia in India and understanding of its psychological effects is required to self-monitor the depended behaviour.¹⁰

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A descriptive study was conducted to assess the risk of developing Nomo phobia among 200 students of selected students in Ludhiana, Punjab. Simple random sampling technique was used for sampling. Findings revealed that majority of the students (79%) were at risk of developing Nomo phobia, followed by 15% normal and remaining (6%) were Nomo phobic. The study shows that majority are at risk of developing Nomo phobia.¹¹

A cross sectional study was done among 130 third year medical students of SAIMS medical college Indore. Most of the students were in the age of 22-24 years. The outcome of result was 83% of student experienced panic attacks when their mobile phone was misplaced. Head ache and lethargy were the common side effects that were experienced by 61% of the student which might be because of overuse of cell phones. 73% of students were Nomo phobic and 21% of Nomo phobic experienced 'Ringxiety'. 61% of students had to recharge once a month, 28% of students had to recharge twice a month and 11% had to recharge three time a month. Study gives a brief idea of woeful outcomes of Nomo phobia.¹²

A Quasi experimental study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge regarding Nomo phobia among students of selected colleges in District Jalandhar Punjab. The sample size was 100 college students and quasi experimental research design was used in the study. There was a significant difference between pre-test and post-test knowledge score was 21.45 in experimental group so research hypothesis (H1) was accepted at $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Hence it was concluded that STP was useful in providing knowledge regarding Nomo phobia.¹³

An evaluation research approach was used to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge regarding health hazards of using mobile phone among high school students in selected schools in Bangalore Karnataka. The mean pre-test knowledge school score was inadequate (70%). The mean post-test knowledge score was improved and found 72%. There was a significant difference between pre-test and post-test knowledge score. So it is evident that STP is significantly effective in improving the knowledge regarding hazards of cell phones.¹⁴

The complexity of this condition is very challenging to the patient family and members as well as for the physicians as Nomo phobia shares common clinical symptoms with other disorders. We have to stay in the real world more than the virtual world. We have to re-establish human-human interaction, face to face connections so we need to limit our use of mobile phones rather than banning it because we cannot escape the force of technological advancements.¹⁵

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

"A study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on identification and management of Nomo Phobia among basic BSc Nursing students at selected college of Nursing in Bangalore"

OBJECTIVES

- To assess the pre-test level of knowledge on identification and management of Nomo phobia among nursing students.
- To assess the effectiveness of structured teaching program on identification and management Nomo phobia among nursing students.
- To find the association between the pre-test level of knowledge on identification and management of Nomo phobia and selected demographic variables of nursing students.

HYPOTHESIS

The hypothesis will be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H1 – There will be a significant improvement in the post-test knowledge score regarding identification and management on Nomo phobia after attending STP as compared to the pre-test scores.

H2- There will be a significant association between pre-test level of knowledge on identification and management of Nomo phobia and the selected demographic variables of nursing students.

LIMITATIONS

- The study is limited to only 60 samples
- The study is limited to Basic BSc nursing students only
- Data collection period is limited to 4 weeks only

METHODOLOGY

The researcher adopted a one group pre-test and post-test research design to evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching programme. The independent variable in the study was structured teaching programme. The dependent variable in the study was knowledge on identification and management of Nomo phobia. The study was conducted in Karnataka college of Nursing, Bangalore. Convenient sampling technique was followed to select the sample. The sample consisted of 60 whom all above 17-18 years and screened the sample by using the inclusive and exclusive criteria. The tool developed and validated by experts; the tool consists of 2 sections. Section I consisted of 12 items related to socio demographic variables, section II consisted of 34 questions related to knowledge. The tool was deemed reliable and feasible by conducting pilot study in Sofia College of nursing. The Cronbach's alpha value of 0.8 indicates good reliability.

Structured teaching programme consisted of general information, signs and symptoms and management of nomophobia Structured teaching programme were prepared to enhance the knowledge of students regarding identification and management of Nomo phobia. The final study was conducted from during June 2020. Pre-test was conducted to assess the level of knowledge and structured teaching programme was given on the same day. Post-test was done after seven days.

RESULT/ DISCUSSION

The data gathered were analysed interpreted in terms of objectives. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for the data analysis. Projected the data analysed using paired 't' test to compare pre-test & post-test knowledge scores to assess the effectiveness of Structured teaching programme on the level of knowledge on identification and management of Nomo phobia among basic BSc Nursing student in selected Nursing colleges.

- During pretest, Majority of 35(58.3%) of the students had moderate knowledge and 25(41.7%) had inadequate knowledge level and posttest shows, Majority of 41(68.3%) of the students had adequate knowledge and 19(31.7%) of the students had moderate knowledge and none of them had inadequate knowledge regarding identification and management of Nomo Phobia .In overall knowledge, the mean% pretest knowledge was 54.167% with SD 14.217%. The mean% posttest knowledge found to be 82.843% with SD 7.888%. However, the enhancement was proved as mean (28.676%) and SD of (8.768%). Further, the paired t-test value (25.312) shows statistical significance at level of $p < 0.001$ with df (59), establishing the effectiveness of treatment.

	Number of questions	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean%	SD%	t value	p value
Pre	34	18.417	4.834	54.167	14.217	25.312	$p < 0.001$ (df=59)
Post	34	28.167	2.682	82.843	7.888		
Enhancement	34	9.75	2.981	28.676	8.768		

- The present study shows that there is no significant association between demographic variables [age, gender, course, area of residence, type of family, occupation of father, occupation of mother, monthly pocket money, birth order, relationship with father and time spent on phone] and pre knowledge regarding effectiveness of structured teaching programme regarding identification and management of Nomo Phobia among BSc students of selected nursing college, Bangalore with $p > 0.05$.

CONCLUSION

The present study showed that B.Sc. nursing students have lack of knowledge on the identification and management of nomophobia. Structured teaching program was found to be effective to enhance their knowledge. Further researches can be conducted to examine various variables and contributing factors to excessive use of mobile and its effect on individual physical, psychological and spiritual dimensions of health among same samples in different areas.

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